

ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

TAGIEVA Gulsum Gafurovna

*Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov
Department of Sociology and Social Work Associate Professor
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14046495>*

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE SOCIAL SECURITY SYSTEM

ANNOTATION

This article is devoted to the topic "Methodological foundations of the development of the social security system", and it is explained that this issue has been of interest to Pythagoras, Heraclitus, Plato, Aristotle, Middle and Near Eastern encyclopedists since ancient times. At the same time, some of our scholars consider the issue of social security implementation as "helplessness - this is fate, other scholars consider hope for the help of others as foolishness. In some scientific sources, social security is on the contrary, concern for the benefit of the "weak", "strangers" is one of the criteria of social justice. as one, and in the Islamic religion, social welfare is to meet the needs of the economically helpless, needy and bereaved sections of society and to establish social justice, and in Islam, social welfare is the introduction of taxes such as zakat, khiraj, and ushr, one of the 5 pillars is zakat, which is it is described that it is oriented towards meeting the needs of the poor and widows. In addition, world-scale models are revealed in the study of social security issues: Germany, Denmark, New Zealand, Great Britain.

Key words: social security, social security in the East, social security in Islam, social security in the West, social security models.

МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена теме "Методологические основы развития системы социального обеспечения", и поясняется, что этот вопрос с древних времен интересовал Пифагора, Гераклита, Платона, Аристотеля, энциклопедистов Ближнего и Среднего Востока. В то же время некоторые наши ученые рассматривают проблему внедрения социального обеспечения как "беспомощность - это судьба", другие ученые считают надежду на помощь других глупостью. В некоторых научных источниках социальная защищенность, наоборот, забота о благе "слабых", "чужих" является одним из критериев социальной справедливости. во-первых, в исламской религии социальное обеспечение направлено на удовлетворение потребностей экономически беспомощных, нуждающихся и обездоленных слоев общества и установление социальной справедливости, а в исламе социальное обеспечение - это введение таких налогов, как закят, хирадж и уshr, одним из 5 столпов которых является закят, который, как описано, ориентирован на удовлетворение потребностей бедных и вдов. Кроме того, при изучении вопросов социального обеспечения выявляются модели мирового масштаба: Германия, Дания, Новая Зеландия, Великобритания.

Ключевые слова: социальное обеспечение, социальное обеспечение на Востоке, социальное обеспечение в исламе, социальное обеспечение на Западе, модели социального обеспечения.

ИЖТИМОЙ РИВОЖЛАНИШНИНГ МЕТОДОЛОГИК АСОСЛАРИ ХАВФСИЗЛИК ТИЗИМИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақола "Ижтимоий таъминот тизими ривожланишининг методологик асослари" мавзусига бағишланган бўлиб, бу масала қадим замонлардан бери Пифагор, Гераклит, Афлотун, Аристотел, Ўрта ва яқин Шарқ энциклопедистларини қизиқтирганлиги тушунтирилади. Шу билан бирга, баъзи олимларимиз ижтимоий таъминотни амалга ошириш масаласини "ночорлик - бу тақдир, бошқа олимлар бошқаларнинг ёрдамига умид қилишни аҳмоқлик деб билишади. Баъзи илмий манбаларда ижтимоий таъминот аксинча, "заиф", "бегоналар" манфаати учун ташвиш ижтимоий адолат мезонларидан биридир. бири сифатида ва Ислом динида ижтимоий таъминот жамиятнинг иқтисодий ночор, муҳтож ва яқинларидан айрилган табақаларининг еҳтиёжларини қондириш ва ижтимоий адолатни ўрнатишдир, Исломда еса ижтимоий таъминот закот, хирож ва ушр каби солиқларни жорий этишдир, 5 устундан бири закотдир, бу камбағал ва бева аёлларнинг еҳтиёжларини қондиришга йўналтирилганлиги тасвирланган. Бундан ташқари, ижтимоий таъминот масалаларини ўрганишда жаҳон миқёсидаги моделлар аниқланади: Германия, Дания, янги Зеландия, Буюк Британия.

Калит сўзлар: ижтимоий хавфсизлик, Шарқда ижтимоий хавфсизлик, Исломда ижтимоий хавфсизлик, Ғарбда ижтимоий хавфсизлик, ижтимоий хавфсизлик моделлари.

Introduction.

Scientists have been interested in the methodological basis of issues of social security system development for a long time. If we refer to the work of the thinkers of the past, most of them laid the foundation for this work by setting such a problem in the most beautiful way. In ancient times, Pythagoras, Heraclitus, Plato, Aristotle, encyclopedic scholars of the Middle and Near East, Abu Nasr Farabi, Khuja Bahavuddin Naqshbandi, Najmiddin Kubro considered helplessness as "destiny" and hoping for help from others as "pride".

On the other hand, concern for the benefit of the "weak" and "strangers" is described as one of the criteria of social justice in the scientific heritage of Abu Raikhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Khoja Ahmad Yasavi, Khoja Ahror Vali, Yusuf Khos Khajib, Nizamulmulk, Alisher Navoi. Great progress was made in ensuring social norms among different layers of the population during the time of Karakhani Ibrahim ibn Nasr, later Sahibqiran Amir Temur and his descendants Umarshaikh Mirza, Ulughbek Mirza, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur [1, 2, 3].

The problems of eliminating social inequality are expressed in the scientific work of modern enlighteners Ahmad Donish, Abdulla Avloni, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov and others. The problem of social security is also given in the holy sources of Islam, the Holy Qur'an and Hadith, which describe the main reasons for social security and ways of social protection.

In Islam, social welfare is a government-level effort to meet the needs of the economically disadvantaged, needy, and destitute sections of society and to establish social justice. It is known from history that Islam has paid great attention to this issue since its early days. Anyone who has studied the introduction of taxes such as zakat, kharaj (khiroj), and ushr and their distribution places knows this well.

Even one of the 5 pillars of Islam is zakat, which is aimed at meeting the needs of the poor and widows, and it is considered a great prayer. Even the fact that Caliph Abu Bakr Siddiq, may God bless him and grant him peace, fought against the tribes that refused to pay zakat shows how important this work is. There are many hadiths about how the accumulated wealth of a person who does not pay zakat will torment him in the Day of Judgment.

Anyone who has studied history, especially the history of Islam, knows very well that the first person who gave allowances to children was the Commander of the Faithful, Umar, may Allah be pleased with him, and the one who first gave a scholarship (scholarship) to his student was Abu Hanifa No'man ibn Thabit, may God bless him and grant him peace¹. People who follow the rules of religion, because of their preoccupation with fulfilling this duty, are deprived of means of livelihood and meeting their needs. As long as they do not fulfill their duties, the pillars of faith (Islam) will not be introduced. Therefore, it is obligatory for the Sultan to provide for them. Then they will have the opportunity to fully fulfill their duties.

Results.

In the Western world, the studies of S. V. Shishkin, V. I. Bogdanovskaya, A. K. Solovyov, N. B. Topka, Z. Zamaraeva, N. A. Volgin, V. P. Galaganov and other thinkers are of great importance. Centuries separate the researches of these scientists, but they are united by the fact that they are among the first and special researches devoted to the problems of social security and social protection.

We believe that it is necessary to study its global models when studying the issues of social security. Social security models used worldwide include:

1. Taxation model (Germany) - depends on how the country taxes its citizens. The most common tax management rule is to levy taxes based on ability to pay.

2. Social Security Model (Germany) – deals with how the state pays unemployment benefits, pensions, maternity leave, parental leave and disability benefits.

3. State Service Model (Denmark, New Zealand) – services such as health care can be financed almost entirely by the public, by private insurance, or somewhere in between. For example, the United Kingdom has an almost entirely publicly funded National Health Service, while Canada offers health services at the provincial level. In contrast, in the US, people must rely on health insurance policies in case of hospitalization, and there is minimal public assistance for poor people. Another element could be public transport, as some countries have nationalized their rapid transit systems while others have privatized them (for example, public transport is privatized in the UK, but not in Northern Ireland).

4. The employment model (UK) – economies with a liberal approach to employment do nothing to ensure job security. Other countries rely on some degree of regulation to protect workers from arbitrary dismissal. High levels of regulation, such as high severance pay, are often cited as a reason for employers' reluctance to hire and unemployment. They have achieved effective results in this regard.

The British model is used in Great Britain, Ireland, Canada, New Zealand, Australia and South Asian countries. The British model has a welfare state that is roughly average compared to high-income OECD (organization of economic cooperation and development) countries. They have high levels of poverty and inequality. Most Western European countries provide health care, redistribute income, and guarantee a living wage income [4].

The continental European model is used in Austria, France, Germany, Belgium and Luxembourg. The Continental model has health and safety regulations and many industry regulations. However, the labor market has proven inflexible and slow to respond to globalization. Insurance contributions are used to reduce poverty and provide high-quality health care, unemployment benefits. In general, this model can be seen as a model between British and Scandinavian models.

The Mediterranean model is used in Italy, Spain, Greece, and Portugal. The Mediterranean model is similar to the Continental model, but focuses wealth on private public pensions. The labor market is inflexible. This model does not work very well in reducing poverty in the lower strata of society.

The Scandinavian model is used in Norway, Sweden, Denmark, Iceland, Finland and the Netherlands. In the Netherlands, the so-called "Scandinavian corporatist" model is due to the strong influence of corporatist elements such as trade unions, and state-funded unemployment benefits among other resources for employers, the general public.

Labor markets remain mobile due to ease of firing and hiring. The government takes care of those who have been laid off with unemployment benefits and retraining. The equality of the Scandinavian model is achieved through taxation. As a result of their policies, Sweden, Denmark and Norway have the lowest income inequality in the world. Scandinavian countries show strong economic growth and productivity growth, but most importantly, they consistently top global happiness surveys.

Social security systems under the Scandinavian model are highly rated even when compared to models that meet many international standards of well-being (eg, the German Economic Forum, 2020). However, as a limited criticism, some Scandinavian social welfare and gender researchers argue that such estimates of welfare, based on simple welfare indicators, may be somewhat superior to the Nordic countries in terms of gender and racial equality.

For example, they recommend that we look at well-being from a broader perspective, including issues related to physical citizenship. One can see that some basic forms of male dominance and white privilege still persist in Scandinavian countries. For example, forced labor against women, sexual violence against children, military, academic and religious violence.

As with social security models, pensions, a type of social security, also have their own models. They are as follows:

"Generational solidarity" model - generation T (let's call it our parents) retired, generation T_1 (children of generation T) pays insurance contributions for generation T to receive pensions, generation T_2 pays pension for generation T_1 , etc. So no fund is created. No one pays for himself, whoever makes a contribution to the pension fund, then he becomes the source of pension funds of the citizen who retired before him.

Unlike other countries, Uzbekistan has an accumulated pension system, which is implemented in a mandatory and voluntary manner. It is mandatory for citizens working in the public sector, and voluntary for self-employed citizens. In our country, the accumulated pension system does not work alone. This system works together with the generational exchange model and we call it a mixed system.

Mixed system - the joint implementation of the solidarity of generations and the accumulated pension system. Today, our country uses a mixed pension system.

In most developed countries, social security, that is, the system of pensions and benefits, is implemented mainly through insurance contributions.

Historically, social security was introduced in Rome by Julius Caesar as a system of military pensions. The first pension system established by the state according to the age of those employed in the private sector was implemented in Germany in 1889. A distinctive feature of the German approach is that social insurance is compulsory and contributory. Both employers and employees will have to contribute to its financing [5].

The system in practice in Germany is based on the practice of voluntary mutual aid funds established by pre-existing guilds and workers' associations. Under the new system, pension entitlement was based on previously paid contributions.

Denmark (1891) and New Zealand (1898) introduced a pension system designed to provide targeted assistance to the poor. Here it would be financed from general tax revenues, provide for means testing and guarantee a flat level of payments. These pension systems evolved largely from traditional poor law.

In the following years, a pension insurance system based on the German model was formed in most of the Western European countries; Anglo-Saxon countries (except the USA) and Northern European countries followed the path suggested by Denmark and New Zealand. These systems solved various tasks. The German system was aimed at maintaining the social status of the working person after retirement, while the Danish system, which was later introduced in England, was aimed at limiting poverty.

The pension systems of developed countries gradually converged in the 20th century. In places (Germany) where the pension system is based on the payment of insurance contributions, guarantees of the minimum amount of the pension are established, which do not depend on previously paid contributions. The pension system is based on equal pensions funded from general revenues, budgets, and needs control has been abolished in recipient countries. In addition to the minimum pension, a mandatory social insurance system was introduced (Great Britain).

In North America, the public old-age pension system is relatively late. Canada introduced a non-contributory means-tested pension system in 1927. In the United States, means-tested pension systems were introduced in the 1920s. By 1934, they were in 28 states. In 1935, the federal system of pension insurance was introduced in the USA.

The way of life, religious ethics, customs and ancient traditions of the Uzbek people indicate that the citizens have been socially protected, albeit little. However, it is observed that this protection does not fully cover all the needy groups and does not have a permanent character.

From the second half of the 19th century, Turkestan became a colony of Tsarist Russia and was ruled by the emperor. No decrees were passed by the emperor concerning the local people on the issue of social welfare.

During the tsar's rule, in 1882-1909, pensions were granted to 14 people in the Syrdarya region, 9 people in the Fergana region, and 2 people in the Samarkand region.

Even though the tsar's government collected waqf taxes from the local people, it spent only 1% of it on pensions, and did not pay attention to health care, education, and social security issues at all.

After 1917, the People's Commissariat for Food Supply was established in the Turkestan region on the issue of social protection. In the period from 1917 to 1922, more than a hundred decrees and decisions related to the issue of social security were adopted. In connection with the central administration of the Republic of Turkestan, orders on social security have been adopted based on decisions and decrees adopted from above.

According to archival sources, on May 13, 1918, the name of the State People's Commissariat was changed to the Labor Commissariat under the name of the Department of People's Social Security, and from November 1919, the People's Commissariat of Social Security became an independent body, and Kurbi was appointed its first commissioner.

The economic situation at that time, famine, unemployment, orphans, and the influx of hungry refugees from various cities of Kazakhstan and Russia to the Republic of Turkestan required that there be a special body in the republic and that this body would deal with the issue of social protection.

This body operated on the basis of the guidelines and instructions of the Russian Social Security Commissariat. The main task was to assign pensions to the defenders of the revolution, their families, the disabled in the ranks of the Red Army, and the family members of the deceased.

In accordance with the Regulation on pension provision adopted on October 31, 1918 and the order of the Central Executive Committee of Turkestan No. 165 of January 3, 1920, 1.5 parts of the average salary for the disabled of the 1st group, the average salary for the disabled of the 2nd group, and the average salary for the disabled of the 3rd group 75% of the salary, 50% of the average salary will be awarded to disabled persons of the 4th group.

On January 20, 1920, according to Resolution No. 185, the amount of survivor's pensions was set at 60 percent of the average salary for one person, 75 percent for two persons, and 100 percent for three persons and more.

The amount of pensions varied with the progress or decline of the society. First, the average pension was 10 soums, then 13.18 soums. The disability pension was 12 soums for the first group, 9 soums for the 2nd group, and 6 soums for the 3rd group.

During this period, many difficulties were encountered in the supply of not only pensions, but also food and clothing. In 1923-1924, a special commission was created to solve the issues of population migration from the Center and drought-prone regions to Turkestan, the presence of famine, social protection, food, housing, and employment, and funds were provided from the state budget and local budgets.

Gradually, old-age pensions were introduced to individuals in some sectors of the national economy.

On February 13, 1930, state pensions began to be regulated by the Regulation "On Social Insurance Pensions and Allowances" of the Central Committee of the USSR. The first section of this Regulation is devoted to disability pensions. The disability pension for general illness depends on the length of service. If a worker becomes disabled or falls ill, regardless of length of service, group 1 general illness disability pension is two-thirds of the average monthly salary, 100 percent for work-disabled persons, will be assigned in reduced amounts to other groups of disabled people. In accordance with the second part of this Regulation, family members who are dependents of deceased persons who died due to a common disease, if there are two members in the family, four-ninths of the average salary of the disabled person, and three-quarters of the average salary for the family members of those who died, bereavement pensions was determined. The third section is related to age-related pensions, the general retirement age is 60 years for men and 55 years for women, the required length of service is 25 years for men and 20 years for women, and the amount of pension is not less than 50 percent of the average salary.

According to the decree of July 3, 1929, teachers were introduced and appointed according to the decree of September 22, 1930, to agronomists in agriculture, according to the decree of September 25, 1929, to medical and veterinary workers in rural areas, according to the decree of October 17, 1933, long-term service pensioners were introduced and appointed to civil aviation.

In the years of the Second World War, several decisions were made to assign pensions and allowances to military personnel and their family members [6, 7].

Allowances were introduced in order to strengthen state support for women with children, mothers with many children and single mothers.

According to the decree of July 1944, the honorary titles "Motherhood Medal", "Motherhood Fame" and "Heroic Mother" were introduced. Since 1947, the regulation on the procedure for assigning allowances to mothers with many children came into force.

On July 14, 1956, the first law "On State Pensions" was adopted. Based on this law, all types of pensions, which were previously assigned on the basis of decrees and decisions, will be assigned on the basis of a single law. However, this law provided for the appointment of disability, old age, survivor's and long-term pensions only for workers and servants.

On July 15, 1964, in connection with the adoption of the Law "On Assigning Pensions and Allowances to Collective Farm Members", a centralized social insurance fund of collective farmers was established, and collective farm members began to receive pensions from this fund from October 1, 1965.

Starting from January 1, 1968, the retirement age of collective farmers was equaled to that of workers and employees, and pension amounts of disabled persons of the 1st and 2nd groups were increased. From this period, disability pensions were also granted to group 3 collective farm members with work disabilities.

On August 3, 1972, the Regulation "On the Procedure for Assigning and Paying State Pensions" was adopted, and several changes were made to the procedure for calculating pensions. Since 1974, this Regulation has set the minimum amount of old-age pension at 45 soums.

In the period between 1970 and 1990, a number of decisions and decrees were adopted to increase the number of pensions and provide them with privileges and reliefs for the disabled people of the Second World War and the family members of those killed in the war.

On August 1, 1989, the small law "On pension provision of the population and non-delayable measures of social service" was adopted, and from that time, the difference between the city and the countryside was eliminated, workers and servants and collective farmers were given uniform pensions on the basis of this law, and until that time the laws have lapsed. All citizens began to use social security equally.

The transition of the country's economy to the order of market relations required a review and deeper reform of the pension provision sector. In this regard, on May 15, 1990, the Law "On pension provision of citizens in the USSR" was adopted and entered into force in 1991. On the basis of the law, reforms in the field of pensions began, and new systems such as state social insurance, social pensions, and income indexation began to be implemented. This law was in force until July 1, 1994, before the law of our independent republic came into force.

On April 28, 1990, the Law "On Pensions of Military Servicemen" was adopted, according to which pensions were assigned to military servicemen, internal affairs bodies, and national security service personnel, and this law is still being followed today.

Conclusion.

It should be noted that Uzbekistan created its own model using the above models. We can see that one of the Uzbek models of social security is mentioned in Article 46 of the newly revised Constitution. It is not an exaggeration to say that "everyone has the right to receive social security in the event of old age, incapacity for work, unemployment, as well as in the event of loss of a breadwinner and in other cases stipulated by the law, it is not an exaggeration to say that this is one of the new steps in the social security."

The amounts of pensions, allowances and other types of social assistance defined by law cannot be less than the officially defined minimum consumption expenses". The new version of the Constitution is a solid guarantee of human honor, dignity and rights.

The new version of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan has created a solid foundation for sustainable development not only in the field of social security, but also in the spheres of statehood, social, political, and economic. This true recognition was specially emphasized in the decree "On preparing for and conducting the celebration of the Constitution Day of the Republic of Uzbekistan" signed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on November 16, 2023.

The fact that 90.21 percent of the citizens who participated in the referendum held in our country on April 30, 2023 voted in favor of the new version of the Constitution clearly confirms this opinion, and at the same time, it expresses that the hopes and aspirations of our people for the establishment of New Uzbekistan were reflected in our General Council. . The people are the only source of state power.

ИҚТИБОСЛАР. СНОСКИ. REFERENCES.

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the new version. 01.05.2023
2. Imam Ghazali. "Forty Hadith Qudsi". - Tashkent.: Tashkent Islamic University publishing-printing association, 2008.-B.3. www.ziyouz.com library
3. Yusuf Khos Hajib Qutadgu bilig: ("Knowledge that brings happiness")/Yusuf Khos Hajib; [Current narrator in Uzbek and author of the foreword is Baqijon Tokhliyev]. — Publishing house named after Cholpon, 2007.; Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf. The difference between poor and needy // <https://islom.uz/maqola/18938>; Alimov U. Child education in the family. Editor-in-Chief: Sheikh Abdulaziz Mansour. - Tashkent: "Movarounnahr", 2014.
4. Volume 7 of "Al-Mawsu'atul fiqhiyya" (Encyclopedia of Islamic jurisprudence).
5. S.V.Shishkin. Social security of economic reforms, -M.: 2002, -572 pages; V.I. Bogdanovskaya. The role of the University of the Third Age in social work with older people. (Postgraduate, Bachelor's, Master's) Monograph. –M.: 2021, -56 pp. A.K. Solovyov. Pension rights of insured persons: problems of formation and risks of implementation. –M.: 2020. -327 pp. N.B.Topka. Social work with disabled people. (Bachelor's degree). Tutorial. –M.: 2021, -400 pp. Z. Zamaraeva. Social protection and social services for the population. –M.: 2017, -175 pp. N.A.Volgin. Fundamentals of a welfare state. – M.: 2019. -421 pp. V.P. Galaganov. Social security law. Workshop. (SPO). Textbook, -M.: 2021, -153 pages,
6. Kasimova G., Botirov A. Funded pension provision. -T.: Civilization. 2015, 31 pages.
7. Sadykova Sh.M. Social assistance for older people. Moscow. Journal Social Policy and Social Partnership. 2008 No. 9. – P.64-67.